

Dinophysis in Puyuhuapi Fjord (Chilean Patagonia): Exploring the Occurrence of Overwintering Populations in the Neuston

Harmful Algal Bloom (HAB) dinoflagellate species may spend their whole life cycle as motile forms in the water column (holoplanktonic) or combine planktonic stages with a substantial part of their life as in dormancy (resting cysts) in the sediments (meroplanktonic). Dinoflagellate resting cysts are sexual life-cycle stages that play a key role in bloom initiation, termination,

and species survival when environmental conditions are not favourable for vegetative growth. The application of cysts in various fields of study, such as palaeoceanography, biogeography, ecology, phylogeny and evolution, has rapidly expanded in recent years [1,2].

The genus *Dinophysis*, includes species which are well known progenitors of one or two groups of lipophilic tox-

ins: i) okadaic acid and dinophysistoxins (aka diarrhetic shellfish poisoning or DSP toxins), and ii) Pectenotoxins. To date, despite abundant field and laboratory studies with established cultures of several species, no sexual cyst forms have been confirmed in the life history of *Dinophysis*. Past reports of putative cyst forms belonging to *Dinophysis acuta*, *D. caudata* and *D. acuminata* turned out to be pellicle (asexual) cysts of *Fragilidium*, a mixoplanktonic dinoflagellate capable of combining phototrophy with heterotrophic feeding on live prey (*Dinophysis* species). Following prey capture of specific *Dinophysis* cells, *Fragilidium* sheds its theca and forms a pellicle cyst which retains the contour of the recently ingested prey [3,4].

Currently, the most accepted hypothesis is that *Dinophysis* species survive winter conditions by adopting quiescent forms with reduced metabolism in a particular water layer until the new growth season begins [5]. Detection and quantification of *Dinophysis* populations that survive after the end of the bloom season may serve as a predictive tool for forthcoming events [6].

In this study we used neuston net hauls (Fig. 1) to explore the presence of overwintering populations of *Dinophysis* in the top 25 cm of the surface water (surface microlayer SML). This SML

Fig. 1. (A). Diagram of the frame holding the neuston net to the vessel; (B). Side view of the neuston net system attached to the vessel; (C). Using the neuston net in Puyuhuapi fjord.

Fig. 2. (A). Map of the study area showing northern Chilean Patagonia inland sea (red square indicates Puyuhuapi Fjord); (B). Puyuhuapi Fjord area and sampling stations (red circles).

Fig. 3. Spatial distribution of *Dinophysis* cells (*Dinophysis acuta*, *D. acuminata* and *D. subcircularis*) recorded in the top 25 cm of the SML at the six stations.

includes the neuston layer, a particular habitat that serves as a refuge for a diverse group of organisms, including phytoplanktonic species [7]. Populations present at very low cell densities are frequently overlooked by conventional sampling methods such as oceanographic bottles, vertical net hauls, or tube samplers.

The study area was Puyuhuapi fjord (44°S, 73°W) in northern Aysén, Chilean Patagonia (Fig. 2), a well-known hotspot for *Dinophysis* (*D. acuminata*, *D. acuta*) populations. This 100-km-long fjord, characterised by a high water renewal time (~300 days in Magdalena Sound), has two connections with oceanic waters located at the mouth (Moraleda Channel) and head (Jacaf Channel). These characteristics make Puyuhuapi Fjord a suitable environment for exchange with open waters, cell accumulation and *Dinophysis* growth [8].

In June (winter) 2024, a three-day cruise was carried out along a longitudinal transect of Puyuhuapi fjord, including Magdalena Sound (Fig. 2). Samples were collected in triplicate at each station using a 3-m-long neuston net (20 µm mesh size) attached to a rectangular metal frame (1 m x 0.5 m). The net was submerged 25 cm deep and hauled from the side of the vessel for 100 m at 1–2 knots. This procedure, repeated three times per station, ensures accurate filtration of the near-surface epineuston and hyponeuston. The filtered material (25 m³ per haul) was resuspended in 1-L bottles and sieved through a 149 µm mesh to remove debris and microzooplankton. The material retained in the 149–20 µm size

fraction was resuspended in 500-ml bottles and preserved with Lugol's iodine solution (final concentration 1%). In the laboratory, total sample volumes were measured before cell counts using Sedgewick-Rafter (1 ml) chambers. The entire chamber surface was examined in three replicates, and the average result was expressed as cells m⁻³.

Three species of *Dinophysis* were identified: *Dinophysis acuminata*, *D. acuta* and *D. subcircularis*. Maximal cell densities were found at the mouth of the fjord (Station 1); densities were very low or below detection limits at the inner station close to the fjord head. *D. acuminata* (2.4 x 10³ cells m⁻³) was the most abundant species, *D. acuta* was rare (max. 40 cells m⁻³) and *D. subcircularis* showed a maximum at Station 1 and remained below 30 cells m⁻³ at the other five stations (Fig. 3). This common distribution pattern for the three species suggests that inoculum populations originate outside the fjord.

In summary, horizontal SML net hauls with a neuston net revealed the presence of winter populations of several *Dinophysis* species. This method substantially improves the detection of low-density populations inhabiting poorly explored parts of the water column. Preliminary results shed light on the potential source of inoculum populations that eventually develop dense blooms in Puyuhuapi fjord. An inoculum that originates in outer parts of the fjord and is subsequently advected and grows in the inner zones may represent a potential mechanism and life-cycle adaptation enabling success in fjord systems

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